

Paper 5

COMPUTER AND INFORMATION SCIENCES (CIS) AS A FIELD OF STUDY IN INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITIES: THE FIELD FOR PROMOTING JOB AND CARRIERS

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Abstract

Computing has changed the entire process of information activities ranging from collection, selection, organization, processing, management to dissemination. The advent of Information Technological tools, viz. Database Technology, Networking Technology, Multimedia Technology, Communication Technology have revolutionized the circle of information management of all types of organizations, institutions and individuals. The growing necessities of Computation and IT in different subjects are the results of creation of new domains such as Health IT. Apart from computation and its application in different subjects in managing information is also an important need of the entities of each and every kind hence gradually many universities were moved on Information Science from IT and subsequently from Health IT to most interdisciplinary Health Information Sciences. But due to the role and interest of Technologies and Computing as an academic programs and departments among the society and individuals many universities worldwide have started Computer & Information Science (i.e. Information Science with focus on Computing or merged CS & IS). India is moving towards a developing nation; here manythings are in progress towards a developed nation. In some of the universities in India programs on such skillful and domain based Information Sciences have been started. The present paper may work as a documentary on Computing related domains to create awareness on information and allied interdisciplinary programs or removing misconception. The Paper is talks about the universities moving in the area of CIS with different degrees etc.

Keywords: Information Technology, Indian Universities, Research and Development, CIS, International Universities, Interdisciplinary Sciences

Introduction

Information Sciences is the broadest field within the category of Information and Computing. Information Science is an interdisciplinary subject which is available and consists with other subjects and fields viz. Computer Science, Computer Engineering, Information Technology, Information Systems, Informatics, Information Management etc [1], [5]. Information Science thus deals with all the characteristics of this fields and in many context it has merged with other domains and fields viz. Information Science and Technology, Information Science and Management, Information Science and Engineering, Information Science and Computing. The example of Computer and Information Science (CIS) is a prime example of merged Information Science domain. Internationally many universities have started programs, events, components and departments in this nomenclature. This paper has tries to explore about the CIS nomenclature availability as a Department and College/ School/ Institute in International universities with available and running programs. Paper highlighted the basic program in these CIS departments leading to Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral programs. The paper highlighted about the emerging program in this fields with different concentration/ focus and specializations in brief manner.

Objectives

The core aim of this paper is include but not limited to the following—

- To learn about the basics of Computing and Information as a field of study.
- To know about the nature and components of Computing and Information Sciences.
- To learn about the Computing and Information Sciences education in India.
- To dig out Computing and Information Sciences departments and units in International universities.
- To learn about the current educational and academic program in Computing and Information Sciences.
- To learn about the challenges and issues of Computing and Information Sciences education in International universities.

Computing and Information as a Field

Computing is one of the important and emerging fields in today's age. It is about the Computation and Information related support. Within Computing the oldest branch is called Computer Science which is concentrated on design and development phase. Moreover it is about the partial software dealing field as well. After Computer Science, another domain gained

popularity called Computer Engineering; this is responsible for design and development with strong focus on hardware and related affairs [2], [4].

With the nomenclature of ‘Computing’ another program has gained popularity, which is available in many universities worldwide. The program specially focused on Software design, development, management and engineering. The branch is closely associated with another branch called ‘Computer Application’; which is mainly available in Indian universities. The branch Computer Application is strongly deals with the software and systems development with partial focus on networking, database and computing [6], [8].

Within Information track, most popular field is Information Technology which is about the Information related affairs with the help of different technologies and components viz. Networking Technology, Database Technology, Web Technology, Multimedia Technology, Communication Technology and so on. The field simultaneously may also focus on Software Technology. ‘Informatics’ is another branch responsible for applied IT and field centric applications. It is about the information affairs leading to information processing, management and dissemination. Informatics and its application in different fields leads the development of other areas viz. Bio Informatics, Geo Informatics, Health Informatics etc [7], [11].

Information Management is a field responsible for information affairs but mainly managing information and contents. Information Management is available with Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral Programs in different universities. Information Systems is another field within Information track responsible for the business solutions and organizational affairs. Applications of IT into business are the core aim and agenda of this field.

ICT (i.e. Information and Communication Technology) is another branch responsible for the informatics practice with special focus on Communication and Networking Technology. ICT is dedicated for the design, development, implementation and administration of communication systems for better information practice [3], [9].

Though apart from these many universities have started merged domain within Computing related track or Information related track viz.

- Computer Science and Technology
- Computer Science and Engineering
- Computing and Information Technology
- Computer and Information Science
- Information Science and Technology
- Information Science and Management

- Information Science and Engineering
- Information Science and Computing etc.

CIS in India

In India, Computer and Information Science field is mainly available with different nomenclatures but mostly available are include—

- Computer Science (available as B.Sc., M.Sc., Doctoral/Ph.D. Degree in Colleges, Universities)
- Computer Science and Engineering (available as BE/B.Tech & ME/MTech, Doctoral Degree in mainly in Engineering Colleges and few universities)
- Information Technology (available as B.Sc., M.Sc., Doctoral/Ph.D. Degree in Colleges, Universities)
- Information Technology as Engineering program (available as BE/B.Tech & ME/MTech, Doctoral Degree in mainly in Engineering Colleges and few universities)

Though apart from these few universities also offered Computer Application as a branch of study with the degrees in BCA (Bachelor of Computer Applications) and MCA (Master of Computer Applications). Most of these are offered in the colleges and under the control of AICTE. Though, some of the universities offered Software Engineering nomenclature with BSc, MSc, BTech, M.Tech. program.

Very few universities offers Computer and Information Science, Information Science nomenclature as well with the degrees BSc and MSc. Though, the interdisciplinary programs are also emerging rapidly in recent past.

CIS in International Universities

Internationally many universities have started academic units with the nomenclature on Computer and Information Science. These universities are spreads in different countries viz. USA, Sweden, Malaysia, Japan, Nigeria, Philippines etc. The table: 1 depicted few universities with academic units and programs in this area.

Table: 1-List of universities associated with CIS programs or nomenclature

Sl. No.	University	Country
1	University of Pennsylvania	USA

2	University of Oregon	USA
3	University of Delaware	USA
4	Cleveland State University	USA
5	Gannon University	USA
6	Malmstens Linköping University	Sweden
7	Towson University	USA
8	Arkansas Tech University	USA
9	University of Northumbria	UK
10	The Ohio State University	USA
11	Clarion University	USA
12	Florida Agriculture and Mechanical University	USA
13	Temple University	USA
14	The University of Mississippi	USA
15	University of Technology, PETRONAS	Malaysia
16	King Saud University	UAE
17	Northeastern University	USA
18	King Mongkut University of Technology North Bangkok	Thailand
19	Keio University	Japan
20	Regis University	USA
21	Indiana University, South Bend	USA
22	University of Gothenburg	Sweden

23	University of Hawaii	USA
24	Mansfield University	USA
25	University of San Carlos	Philippines
26	Southwest Baptist University	USA
27	Covenant University	Nigeria
28	Linköping University	Sweden
29	Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology	Japan
30	Sojo University	Japan
31	Ibaraki University	Japan
32	Hosei University	Japan
33	The University of Alabama at Birmingham	USA

The methodology adopted for this study is include the general search strategy with the keywords Department of Computer and Information Science and from the result we have selected up to 10 results [3], [9], [10].

CIS and Future Potentialities

The universities which are started Computer and Information Science nomenclature or programs within CIS related departments and units are include traditional Computer Science, Computer Engineering, Information Technology to Specific Computer and Information Science. And more clearly many other small and specialized fields viz.—

- Bio Informatics & Computational Biology
- Embedded Systems
- Digital Media Design
- Network and Social Systems Engineering
- Software Engineering

- Information Science
- Cyber Security
- Data Science etc

Moreover many universities have started programs as a specializations viz. University of Northumbria, UK etc. Here Table: 2 depicted the details of programs with award, specializations and major subjects.

Table: 2-Details of CIS programs (broad/major or micro) in few selected universities

Sl. No.	University	Country
1	University of Pennsylvania, USA	USA
	<p>Bachelors:</p> <p>BS (Engineering)-Computer Science</p> <p>BS (Engineering)-Computer Engineering</p> <p>BS (Engineering)-Computer Science</p> <p>BS (Engineering)-Digital Media Design</p> <p>BS (Engineering)-Network and Social Systems Engineering</p> <p>Bachelor of Applied Science (Computer Science)</p> <p>Bachelor of Applied Science (Computational Biology)</p> <p>Bachelor of Applied Science (Computer and Cognitive Science)</p>	
	<p>Masters</p> <p>Master of Computer & Information Technology</p> <p>MS (Engineering) CIS</p> <p>MS (Engineering) Embedded Systems</p>	
	<p>Doctoral</p>	

	PhD-CIS	
2	University of Oregon	USA
	<p style="text-align: center;">Bachelors</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BS (CIS)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BS (Mathematics & Computer Science)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BA (CIS)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BA (Mathematics & Computer Science)</p>	<p>Remarks:</p> <p>Offers Minor CIS</p> <p>Offers Minor CIT</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Masters</p> <p style="text-align: center;">MS (CIS)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">MA (CIS)</p>	
	<p style="text-align: center;">Doctoral</p> <p style="text-align: center;">PhD (CIS)</p>	
3	University of Delaware	USA
	<p style="text-align: center;">Bachelors</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BA (Computer Science)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BS (Computer Science)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BS (Information Systems)</p>	<p>Remarks:</p> <p>Certificate in CSE</p> <p>Certificate in Bio Informatics</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Masters</p> <p style="text-align: center;">MS (Computer Science)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">MS (Bio Informatics & Computational Biology)</p>	
	<p style="text-align: center;">PhD (CS)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">PhD (Bio Informatics & Computational Biology)</p>	

4	Cleveland State University	USA
	Bachelors BS (Computer & Information Science)	
5	Gannon University	USA
	No Bachelors in CIS offered	
	Masters MS-CIS (Data Science) MS-CIS (Information Technology) MS-CIS (Software Engineering)	
6	Towson University	USA
	Bachelors	
	Masters MS (Computer Science) MS (Applied Information Technology)	
	Doctor D.Sc. (Information Technology)	
7	Arkansas Tech University	USA
	Bachelors BS (Computer Science) BS (Computer Science Education) BS (Information Technology) BS (Information Systems)	Associate in IT Associate in Cyber Security

	Masters MS (Information Technology)	
8	University of Northumbria	UK
	Bachelors BSc (Applied Computing-Top Up) BSc (Computer Science) BSc (Computer Science with AI) BSc (Computer Science with Game Development) BSc (Computer Networks & Computer Security) BSc (Computer & Digital Forensic) BSc (Information Technology Management for Business)	
	Masters MSc (Information Science-Data Analytics) MSc (Information Science-Library Management) MSc (Computer Science) MSc (Computer Science with Advanced Practice) MSc (Advanced Computer Science) MSc (Computing & Information Technology) MSc (Computing & Information Technology with Advanced Practice) MSc (Computing & Technology) MSc (Cyber Security)	

	<p>MSc (Cyber Security Technology)</p> <p>MSc (Cyber Security with Advance Practice)</p> <p>MSc (Information Security Management)</p> <p>MSc (Web & Mobile Development Technologies)</p> <p>MComp (Computer Science)</p> <p>MComp (Computer & Information Science)</p> <p>MComp (Computer Networks & Cyber Security)</p> <p>MComp (Computer Science with Artificial Intelligence)</p> <p>MComp (Computer Science with Game Development)</p> <p>MComp (Computer Science with Web Develment)</p>	
9	The Ohio State University	USA
	<p>Bachelors</p> <p>BS (CIS)</p> <p>BA (CIS)</p>	Minor in CIS
10	Clarion University	USA
	<p>Bachelors</p> <p>BS (Computer Science)</p> <p>BS (Information Systems)</p>	<p>Minor in Information Systems</p> <p>Minor in Web Development</p>
	<p>Masters</p> <p>MS (Applied Data Analytics)</p>	Minor in Data Analytics
11	Florida Agriculture and Mechanical University	USA
	Bachelors	Minor:

	BS (Computer Science) BS (Computer Information Systems) BS (Information Technology)	Information Technology Computer Information Systems
	Masters MS (Computer Engineering) MS (Software Engineering)	Computer Science Cyber Security Certificate in Cyber Security Certificate in Health Information Privacy & Security
12	The University of Mississippi	USA
	MS (Engineering Science): Computer Science	
	PhD (Engineering Science): Computer Science	
13	University of Technology, PETRONAS	Malaysia
	Bachelors BTech (Hons) Business IT BTech (Hons) ICT	
	Masters MSc (Information Technology)	
	Doctoral PhD (Information Technology)	
14	King Saud University	UAE
	Bachelors	

	<p>BSc (Computer Science)</p> <p>BSc (Computer Engineering)</p> <p>BSc (Information Systems)</p> <p>BSc (Software Engineering)</p> <p>BSc (Information Technology)</p>	
	<p>Masters</p> <p>MSc (Computer Science-Thesis)</p> <p>MSc (Computer Science-Coursework)</p> <p>MSc (Computer Engineering)</p> <p>MSc (Information Systems-Thesis)</p> <p>MSc (Information Systems-Coursework)</p> <p>MSc (Software Engineering-Thesis)</p> <p>MSc (Software Engineering-Coursework)</p> <p>MSc (Information Technology)</p>	
	<p>Doctoral</p> <p>PhD (Computer Science)</p> <p>PhD (Computer Engineering)</p> <p>PhD (Information Systems)</p>	
15	Northeastern University	USA
	<p>Bachelors</p> <p>BS (Computer Science)</p> <p>BA (Computer Science)</p> <p>BS Computer Science + BS Information Science</p>	

	<p>(Combined)</p> <p>BS (Cyber Security)</p> <p>BS (Data Science)</p> <p>BS (CS with Major in Arts Subjects)</p> <p>BS (CS with Major in Science Subjects)</p>	
	<p>Masters</p> <p>MS (Computer Science)</p> <p>MS (Data Science)</p> <p>MS (Cyber Security)</p> <p>MS (Artificial Intelligence)</p> <p>MS (Game Science and Design)</p> <p>MS (Health Data Analytics)</p> <p>MS (Health Informatics)</p> <p>MS (Robotics)</p>	

The universities are improving by introducing new age and new skill based programs and courses which include general Computing and Information related subjects viz. Computer Science, Computer Engineering, Computing, Information Technology to domain specific viz. Health Informatics, Health Data Analytics, Bio Informatics, Computational Biology etc.

Conclusion

The world is become interdisciplinary in nature and universities are moving towards introducing industry and academia ready products. There are many universities which are offering skill based and more specific programs viz. Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Cyber Security, Game Science, Data Science, Data Analytics, Web and Mobile Application Development, Computer Networks etc. The business specific IT programs are also offered by few universities available with the nomenclature of Information Systems. Similar to these universities many other universities

situated in undeveloped nations like India have also started departments and programs in this areas viz. Srinivas University, Karnataka; Raiganj University, West Bengal; Annamalai University, Tamilnadu etc. The industry linkage though also important and required for sophisticated and solid delivery of the programs as well.

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